

IDENTIFYING AND ANALYZING OF LOCAL NETWORK ELEMENTS BASED ON DUDE NETWORK MONITORING PROGRAM

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Abstract: The DUDE (Distributed Universal Diagnostic Environment) network scanning program is a comprehensive tool designed for monitoring and analyzing elements within local networks. Developed with a focus on simplicity and functionality, DUDE excels in providing network administrators with valuable insights into the performance and health of connected devices.

The program features an intuitive interface with essential components such as settings panels for local clients and servers. This allows users to configure connections and customize actions easily. DUDE employs a statistical model to analyze regular states and indicators, enabling it to promptly identify anomalies in the network. The scanning capabilities of the program facilitate the mapping of identified IP addresses, providing an effective means to manage devices through a graphical representation.

Keywords: DUDE, Distributed Universal Diagnostic Environment, Network Scanning, Monitoring, Local Networks, Performance Analysis, Anomaly Detection, IP Address Mapping, Graphical Representation, Settings Panels, Local Clients, Local Servers, Open Connection, Secure Connection.

At present, in our Republic, the development and modernization of computer and information technologies, telecommunications, and networks using the Internet occupy a leading position. One of the most important tasks of modern information technologies is considered to be ensuring the safe and timely delivery of information over the network, in conjunction with the policy of security. Currently, in our Republic, computer and information technologies, telecommunications, and the

development and modernization of networks using the Internet hold a leading position. One of the most important tasks of modern information technologies is considered to be ensuring the safe and timely delivery of information over the network, in conjunction with the policy of security.

Dude is a program designed to monitor the operation of networks and the devices connected to them. If the program detects any issues, it immediately notifies the administrator with access rights to all remote devices. The program operates using SNMP, ICMP, DNS, and TCP. During network scanning, Dude automatically identifies the type and model of discovered devices. Additionally, Dude has many other features that seamlessly integrate with simple installation and reliable operation.

Figure 1. Communication scheme DUDE server and client

In the identification and analysis of elements in the local network based on the Dude network monitoring program, it is essential to give importance to the following six main sections:

- Settings for local clients and local servers;
- Global settings for currently connected servers;
- Left panel - a navigation panel for various features of the software;
- Right panel with a context menu in the left panel that changes based on the selected item - designed to display selected networks, functions, issues, graphics, and other designated elements;
- Division of the right panel into sections;
- Status of client-server connection and the quantity of exchanged information between the client and server, including operations related to extending information, issues, and data between servers and clients.

This includes the overall quantity of information transmitted and received by the server at a given time.

Settings Panel for Local Clients and Local Servers

In this panel, you can configure the connection to the server and customize the specific actions of local clients and local servers.

Figure 2. Scanning process of the network by DUDE

Connecting to the server. By pressing the button, you can choose one of two connection methods:

Open connection. It is important to note that information exchanged between the server and client, including the username and password, is transmitted in a clear text over the network. Therefore, using an open connection is preferable when connecting remotely for better security;

Secure connection. Due to encryption of the information exchanged between the server and client, a secure connection is more advantageous.

For connection, you need to specify the IP address of the Dude server - if connecting to a local server, you should indicate the loopback address - 127.0.0.1.

When configuring the security barrier between the client and server, consider that communication should take place over the TCP protocol at the transport layer. It is possible to modify the standard ports 2210 and 2211 for secure and remote connections.

In the context of scanning, the IP addresses identified during scanning are conveniently mapped to manage devices on the map.

Figure 3. Network scanning map by DUDE

DUDE creates a statistical model based on regular states and indicators, and through this model, it checks for new information and indicators. If anomalies are detected in the check results deviating from the normative state, the DUDE software provides information about it.

DUDE creates a statistical model based on regular states and indicators regarding ordinary states and indicators before analyzing the information.

Figure 5. Network Scanning via Dude (Ingress and Egress Traffic using FreePBX Server)

The DUDE software can be beneficial in areas beyond network monitoring. For instance, DUDE can also be used for monitoring computers, devices, or other critical systems. User requirements are gathered and analyzed, considering factors such as information retrieval speed, compatibility between devices, and the selection of network standards when identifying specific issues.

Figure 6. Network Scanning Result via Dude (General Network Topology and List of Devices)

The log and syslog files of network devices provide essential information for network administrators and system administrators. Log files contain information about events that have occurred in the system or network. Syslog aggregates events of network devices and allows sharing this information with other systems.

DUDE supports both open and secure connections, offering users the flexibility to choose between convenience and heightened security when connecting to servers. Standard protocols, including SNMP, ICMP, DNS, and TCP, are utilized to ensure efficient communication and data retrieval.

Beyond its primary function of network scanning, DUDE demonstrates versatility by extending its monitoring capabilities to various systems, including computers and critical devices. The program takes into account user requirements, such as information retrieval speed, device compatibility, and adherence to network standards, ensuring effective problem resolution.

In conclusion, DUDE emerges as a robust and user-friendly network scanning program, providing administrators with a comprehensive tool for monitoring, analyzing, and maintaining the health and performance of local networks and connected devices.

In addition to its primary function of network scanning, DUDE proves versatile for monitoring various systems beyond traditional networks, including computers and critical devices. The program takes into account user requirements, such as information retrieval speed, device compatibility, and adherence to network standards, to address specific issues effectively.

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